

GS 79
SPHINX
June 27, 1979

Slope of the O.K. Rubble, clay, locus under the displaced core blocks

A general slope downward to the south, must have obtained when the deposits under the displaced core blocks were laid down, and the deposits found in Ns 78, sloping down to the S (the tentatively O.K. deposits), must so slope not only because of denudation from excavations (of S.H.). That there was originally such a slope to these deposits is shown by the fact that cbA, under the SE corner of the Amenhotep Temple, sits considerably higher, on the rubble O.K. locus, than cbB, which is tilted downward to the south. cbC-D then sits low near the bedrock floor. This may indicate that the cb.s and the deposit they rest upon represent a "frozen moment" in the bringing in of cb.s for the construction, uncompleted, of the NW corner of the Sphinx Temple. They were being brought in from the higher unquarried limestone ridge to the N (forming the N side of the corridor N of the S.T.) and down into the NE corner of the Sphinx Sanctuary.

The cut lines, indicating an ancient excavation, filled with clean sand and concentrated limestone chips interspersed, may indicate an operation of digging under the core blocks to remove them. This would have been during plunder operations, and may have been done from a pit dug into the working/~~debris~~ debris filling the general NW corner of the Sphinx Temple.

Rectangular Floor Cuttings - Groups of 3

The rectangular cuttings, at gradients, in the floor in the NE corner of the Sphinx Sanctuary, particularly in the rectangular anomalous rough area, occur in groups of 3, in a line. These seem to have been for lower large cb.s into place as indicated by a group of 3 on line with the large cb forming the NW corner block of the Sphinx Temple (Fc 1-2-3, cut into the floor of the bedrock ledge in the NW corner of the S.T.). These are almost exactly on line with the S side of this large cb, while Fc3, the W most of this group, is exactly under the curved N edge of the shorter cb bridging the space in the NW corner of the S.T., W wall.

The angle and direction of the ~~gradients~~ gradients of the cuttings indicate the direction of setting in stones (?). A pattern with associated "post holes" is more in question, as there are no such holes associated with Fc 1-2-3. Another group of 3, Fc 4-5-6 occurs exactly under the N side of cbC, or the S side of adjacent cbB. The anomalous area in the floor of the NE corner of the sanctuary thus seems to indicate some kind of working with heavy cb.s. This must have been after the floor of the sanctuary

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was levelled, as the anomalous rough area interrupts otherwise generally levelled bedrock floor (average about 10.62 elevation). The granite dustm found last year in features like Fc19, and this year in Fh5, indicates that the activity involved fine scrapping or sanding of granite. Yet all of this activity must have been before the depositing of the tentatively O.K. rubble loci of R5-6, R10, R2, as in R10, this rubble covers the leveled parts of the floor, the cuttings, and their gypsum fill. The holes and cuttings seem to have been filled with gypsum to relevel this area of the sanctuary floor after the activity, judging from the section through the deposits in Fh5.

The cuttings cleared in the Area N last year, also rectangular and at a gradient, occur again in a group of 3. This pattern should be looked for at others places, such as the Valley Temple, other places in the Sphinx Temple, etc.